

International Online Conference
Sustainable Technologies in Water Treatment and Desalination
28 - 29 January 2022

National Institute of Technology Calicut - India

Qualitative point-of-care detection of heavy metals and effluents with a modified micro-biome-based biosensor

Presenter:

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Overview

- Brief on Heavy Metal Pollution
- Why be concerned?
- The Solution
- Biosensors – In Brief
- Microbial Biosensors – In Brief
- Why Microorganisms?
- Future scope – Bioremediation & Bio-refinery
- Acknowledgments

Brief on Heavy Metal Pollution – Common Everyday Heavy Metals

- Titanium
- Vanadium
- Chromium
- Manganese
- Iron
- Cobalt
- Nickel
- Copper
- Zinc
- Arsenic
- Molybdenum
- Silver
- Cadmium
- Tin
- Platinum
- Gold
- Mercury
- Lead

Brief on Heavy Metal Pollution – Natural Origins

Geldingadalsgos eruption at dawn in Iceland
March 2021

Photo Credits: Andrii Gladii

Devil's Bridge in the municipality of Santander,
January 20222

Photo Credits: Emilio Gómez Fernández

Source: Wikimedia Commons, Creative Commons License

Brief on Heavy Metal Pollution – Anthropogenic Origins – Industrial

Smoke Discharge by a Factory in Sweden
January 2017
Photo Credits: Anonymous

Wastewater Discharge by a Factory in Belgium
November 2018
Photo Credits: Anonymous

Source: Wikimedia Commons, Creative Commons License

Brief on Heavy Metal Pollution – Anthropogenic Origins – Urban Residential

Garbage littered in Hoogly River in India
September 2018
Photo Credits: Pradip Paswan

Landfill at Guwahati in India
March 2018
Photo Credits: Mike Prince

Swage Runoff in Canada
April 2018
Photo Credits: Finn Terman Frederiksen

Source: Wikimedia Commons, Creative Commons License

Why be concerned?

Figure 1: Exposure Pathway to Humans in Nature

Source:

Human Health Risk Assessment for Inhabitants of Four Towns of Rajshahi, Bangladesh due to Arsenic, Cadmium and Lead Exposure, 2018
[DOI: 10.14456/ea.2018.13](https://doi.org/10.14456/ea.2018.13)
 Public Full-Text on ResearchGate

Why be concerned?

- Oxidative Stress
- Free Radical Formation
- Fenton Reactions

Figure 2: Consequence of Extensive Human Exposure to Heavy Metals

Source:

Heavy metal pollution in the environment and their toxicological effects on humans, 2020

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04691>

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Why be concerned? (cont.)

Figure 3: Metal-induced oxidative stress pathway

Figure 4: Chromium formation of free radicals

Source:

Heavy metal pollution in the environment and their toxicological effects on humans

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04691>

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Why be concerned? (cont.)

Superoxide ($\bullet\text{O}_2^-$) is generated from the decomposition of H_2O_2 , by cobalt, especially Co^{2+} .

Figure 5: Fenton Reactions by (a) Cobalt and (b) Copper

Source:

Heavy metal pollution in the environment and their toxicological effects on humans

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04691>

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The Solution

- 8 R's of recycling
Recycle – Refuse – Reduce – Reuse – Repair – Re-gift – Recover – Rethink
- Green alternatives
Energy – Materials – Infrastructures – Manufacturing – Waste Management
- Stricter Environmental Regulations and their Enforcement

Biosensors – In Brief

Figure 6: Schematic Diagram of a Typical Biosensor

Source:

Electrochemical Biosensor Based on Microfabricated Electrode Arrays for Life Sciences Applications (Thesis), 2014
[DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11066.49603](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11066.49603)

Public Full-Text on ResearchGate

Microbial Biosensor – In Brief

Figure 7:

(a) Domain Structure of Bacterial two-component regulatory systems (TCRS).

(b) A multi-component phosphorelay system containing the HAMP, PAS, and phosphotransfer domains.

Source:

Engineered microbial biosensors based on bacterial two-component systems as synthetic biotechnology platforms in bioremediation and bio-refinery, 2017

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12934-017-0675-z>

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Why Microorganisms?

Figure 8: Advantages, limitations and circumvention of conventional obstacles in Microbial Biosensors

Source:

Review of micro/nanotechnologies for microbial biosensors, 2015

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2015.00061>

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Future Scope – Bioremediation & Bio-refinery

Figure 9: Application of TCRSs in bioremediation and microbial bio-refinery.

Source:

Engineered microbial biosensors based on bacterial two-component systems as synthetic biotechnology platforms in bioremediation and bio-refinery, 2017

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12934-017-0675-z>

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Thank
You

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